

EFFECTS OF MOTIVATION IN PARTICIPATING TO CROSSFIT CENTERS WITH THE PURPOSE OF RECREATIVE EXERCISE

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Abstract:

The purpose of this research is to determine the factors of influence of the individuals who do exercise in the Crossfit centers in Istanbul for recreational purposes and to relate these factors to some variables. The sample group of this experiment consists of individuals that do exercise in the Crossfit centers in Istanbul for recreational purposes. For the means of collecting data, "Recreational Exercise Motivation Scale" (REMM), which is developed to determine the factors of motivation for individuals to do recreational exercise, is used. To determine the recreational exercise motivations of participants, t-test is used for Independent Groups according to their gender variable. T-test for Independent Groups has been used to determine the recreational exercise motivation of participants with regard to gender type variable. A difference has been found in rivalry sub-dimension of REMM scale according to gender variable in the participants that go to the crossfit centers ($p < 0.05$). When the data from this research have been examined, male individuals who go to the CrossFit centers participate more to the exercises with competitive reasons than female individuals.

Keywords: recreation, free time, leisure time, motivation, sports, crossfit

1. Introduction

Reasons behind the participation of individuals to recreative sports events are drawing the interest of scientists for a long time. There has been lots of research conducted in the areas of sports, exercise, and recreation to recognize and determine the factors that motivate individuals to this kind of events. These studies are mainly to interpret the reasons of individuals for participating in the recreative sports activities. There are three theories in this field. First theory is Self-Determination Theory, SDT, which is formed and conceptualized by Deci and Ryan (Deci 1975, Deci and Ryan 1985), second theory is

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Achievement Goal Theory, AGT, (Ames 1992, Dweck 1986, Nicholls 1989, Robert 1993) and the third one is Requirement Theory, RT (İbrahim and Cordes, 2002).

According to STD, there are three states that motivate individuals. These are; demotivation, state of inner motivation and state of outer motivation. Therefore, factors that motivate individuals are discussed in two different angles. From these motivational factors, inner motivation is provided with internal factors, outer motivation is provided with external factors. With what frequency of external and internal factors perceived as stimulating and stimuli that caused by the participation of recreational sports/exercises are concerns of these theories since it causes motivational differentiation (Fuzhong, 1999). In addition to the benefits that are obtained with inner and outer motivation from the individuals, the purpose of the event is a leading factor that motivates individuals for recreational exercises/sports. External factors are more of a stir for the inner motivational state. For instance, the inner motivational purpose of an individual who jogs for physical health is his/her vitality whereas the companion, the whereabouts and the frequency of occurrence of this event are about external motivational factors as much as it is about internal motivational factors. (Şahin, 1999)

AGT is, from a logical point of view, an extended version of Bandura's Self Efficacy Theory and Harter's Effectance Motivation Theory. According to Nicholls, the definitional property of achievement motivation rests on the perception one's self-talents. Moreover, Nicholls focused on goal-oriented nature of success behavior and discussed talent perception which is a distinguished quality of achievement motivation. Achievement Goal Theorem suggests that there are two goals of achievement in an environment of success. These achievement goals identified by Nicholls (1992) as duty participation and ego participation (Tiryaki, 2000 Toros, 2001). The purpose of this research is to analyze factors that motivate individuals who have participated to recreational exercises in fitness and crossfit centers and to compare the participation reasons according to some demographical variables.

2. Material and Methods

Research group consists of individuals who have participated to recreative exercises in crossfit centers. Since most cities in Turkey have no crossfit center, the city of İstanbul has been chosen as the sample group to reach the necessary amount of members. Participants of crossfit have been selected from CrossFit Taxim, Antrum CrossFit and CrossFit 34.

A questionnaire carried out as the primary data collection method. REMS is developed by Helen Rogers and Tony Morris (2003) and validity and reliability test has been done by Gürbüz, Aşçı, and Çelebi (2006).

Recreational Exercise Motivation Scale (REMM) broadly evaluates factors that motivate individuals to a recreational physical activity.

To determine the adequate sample number for the research, power analysis has been made before the data collection stage. The venues for which the questionnaire can be carried out are determined, reached and necessary permits are taken.

The data that is obtained from the research is transferred to SPSS 22.0 program. To define the sample group specifications in data analysis, descriptive statistical analysis (average, standard deviation, frequency, and percentage) has been made.

3. Results and Discussion

These results were obtained from the information collected in research.

Table 1: Demographic Information

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Female	39	19,5
Male	161	80,5
Total	200	100
Education	Frequency	Percentage
Middle school	2	1,0
High school	15	7,5
Associate	16	8,0
Undergraduate	109	54,5
Postgraduate	58	29,0
Total	200	100
Age	Frequency	Average
18-22	15	7,5
23-27	45	22,5
28-32	56	28,0
33-37	60	30,0
38-42	12	6,0
43 and older	12	6,0
Total	200	100
Personal income	Frequency	Average
0-499 TL	8	4,0
500-999 TL	5	2,5
1000-1499 TL	8	4,0
1500-1999 TL	12	6,0
2000 TL and above	167	83,5
Total	200	100

Demographic information of the participants is given in table-1 for whom the REMM is applied. When the data of the research is examined it can be observed that most of the participants are male, an age of 23-37, has an income of 2000TL and above.

Table 2: Comparison of Crossfit Exercise Type with Gender Variable According to Recreational Exercise Motivation Scale of Individuals That Participated in the Research

REMM Sub Dimension (Crossfit)	Gender	n	Avg.	SS	t	P
Health	Male	161	92,95	11,10	-210	,835
	Female	39	93,48	14,81		
Rivalry	Male	161	35,16	9,18	2,240	,029*
	Female	39	31,00	10,68		
Body and Physical Appearance	Male	161	41,49	6,79	,453	,652
	Female	39	40,89	7,55		
Social and Entertainment	Male	161	36,55	8,55	,098	,923
	Female	39	36,41	8,08		
Skill Development	Male	161	33,31	4,50	-,059	,957
	Female	39	33,35	5,15		

*: P<0,05

According to Independent Groups t-test results (Table 2), averages taken from rivalry sub-dimensions of the REMM scale of participants that does crossfit, is found different with respect to gender variable.

Table 3: The Results of Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Analysis Aimed at Determining the Relation between Exercise Duration of Participants and Sub-Dimensions of REMM Scale

	1	2	3	4	5
1 Health					
2 Competition	,11**				
3 Physical Appearance	,40**	,47**			
4 Social and Fun	,33**	,56**	,23**		
5 Skill Development	,71**	,22**	,28**	,36**	
6 Exercise Duration	,17**	,17**	-,08	,22**	,21**

P<0,01

According to table 6, there is no dependency between the sport condition of father and his child. While %8,9 of the students whose fathers are playing sports, %60,6 of them whose fathers aren't playing sports do this activity. The relation between the sub-dimensions of REMM scale and participants 'Exercise Duration is analysed with sub-dimensions of Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Analysis. The results of Correlation analysis are shown at Table 3. As It seems in Table 3, there is a positive relation (p<0.01) between health sub-dimension of REMM scale and physical appearance (r=.40), social and fun (r=.33), skill development (r=.71).

There is a positive relation between competition (r= .11) and exercise duration (r= .17) but It is not significant. Besides, there are positive significant relations between competition sub-dimension and physical appearance (r= .47), social and fun (r= .56) skill development (r= .22) exercise duration (r= .17), there is not a significant relation between exercise duration (p<0.01). While there is a positive significant relation (p<0.01) between physical appearance sub-dimension of REMM and social and fun (r= .23), skill development (r= .28) there is not a negative significant relation with exercise duration (p>0.01). There is a positive significant relation between social and fun sub-dimension

of REMM and skill development ($r = .36$), its sub-dimensions and exercise duration ($r = .22$). Also, there is a positive significant relation between exercise duration ($r = .21$) and skill development ($p < 0.01$).

4. Conclusion

Differences have been found between motivation factors that affect individuals to participate in recreative sports and some of the demographical parameters in some variables of REMM's health, rivalry, physical appearance, social/entertainment and skill development sub-dimensions.

The researches that study whether the motivation for exercise differentiates with respect to gender indicates that females less often do exercises with the intention of physical appearance and social relations whereas males do exercises with the motivation of rivalry and competence (Ryan et al. 1997: 335-354). On the contrary, there are many researches that indicate females participate exercises with inner motivations more when compared to males (Landry and Solmon, 2004: 457-369, Wilson et al. 2003: 294-306); and males does exercise less with outer reasons (Annesi J.: 2004: 5, Frederick et al. 1996: 691-701). In this sense, it coincides with the study in hand since there are reasonable differences between exercise motivations of male and female participants. A reasonable difference has been found in the rivalry sub-dimension when factors of motivation that effects participation to the crossfit centers with recreative event purposes examined according to the REMM scale with respect to the gender variable. As a result, it is observed that male participants attend to exercises in crossfit centers with competitive reasons more than female participants. It is seen that Fisher et al. (2016: 10) found a reasonable difference at rivalry in terms of gender. Glassman (2007: 2) observed that during the crossfit exercise, males struggle to the death for the sake of points and while using the white-boards as a scoreboard, they logged the records. This environment created the rivalry. In accordance with the data, a conclusion can be made that because of this reason rivalry factor is different between males and females.

Willis and Campbell (1992) made this research on individuals that have participated to long-term physical activities by using Pearson's Product-Moment Correlation Analysis oriented at determining the relation between participant's exercise duration and sub-dimensions of REMM scale. They deduced that participants maintained these activities because they find the amusing. The results support the research. Individuals who have participated long-term exercises state that they have more positive self-representation and motivate more exercise (Altıntaş, Aşçı ve Özdemir, 2007: 912). As a consequence, there is not a relation between individuals' exercise duration and their health, competition, physical appearances but social and fun, skill development. Besides, while health, competition, social and fun, skill development affect positively, physical appearance affects in negative way.

References

1. Altıntaş, A., Aşçı, F. H. and Özdemir, B. T. (2007). Benlik sunumunun cinsiyet ve egzersiz davranışı parametrelerine göre incelenmesi Hacettepe Üniversitesi Spor Bilimleri Dergisi. 18(2).
2. Ames, C. (1992). Classrooms: Goals, structures and student motivation. *Journal of Education Psychology*.
3. Annesi, J.J. (2004). Relationship of Perceived Health and Appearance Improvement, and Self-Motivation, With Adherence to Exercise in Previously Sedentary Women, *European Journal of Sport Science*, vol. 4, issue 2: 5.
4. Deci, E. L. And Ryan, R. M. (2002). *Handbook of self-determination research*. Rochester, NY: University of Rochester Press.
5. Deci, E. L. (1975). *Intrinsic motivation*. New York: Plenum Press.
6. Dweck, C. (1986). Motivational processes affectin in learning. *American Psychologist*
7. Frederick, C.M., Morrison, C. And Manning, T. (1996). Motivation to participate exercise affect and out come behaviors toward physical activity, *Perceptual and Motor Skills*, 82.
8. Fisher, J., Sales, A., Carlson, L., Steele, J., (2016). A Comparison of the motivational factors between crossfit participants and other resistance exercise modalities; A Pilot Study, *The Journal of Sports Medicine And Physical Fitness*.
9. Glassman, G. (2007). "Understanding CrossFit," *CrossFit Journal* 56, April,1.
10. Ibrahim, H., Cordes, K.A., (2002). *Outdoor Reaction, Enrichment For a Lifetime*. Second Edition, Sagamore Publishing, II.
11. Nicholls, J. (1989). *The competitive ethos and democratic education*, MA: Harvard University Press, Cambridge
12. Landry, J.B. and Solmon, M.A. (2004). African American women's self-determination across the Stages of Change for Exercise. *Journal of Sport and Exercise Psychology*, 26.
13. Roberts, G. (1993). *Motivation in sport: Understanding and enhancing the motivation and achievement of children*. In R. N. Singer, M. Murphy, ve C. K. Tennant (Eds.), *Handbook of research on sport psychology*. New York: Macmillan.
14. Ryan, R.M., Frederick, C.M., Lipes, D., Rubio, N. And Sheldon, K.M. (1997). Intrinsic motivation and exercise adherence. *International Journal of Sport Psychology*, 28.
15. Şahin, H. (1999). Kuşak Değişimi, *Radikal Gazetesi*, 25/09/1999.
16. Tiryaki, Ş. (2000). *Spor Psikolojisi: Kavramlar, Kuramlar ve Uygulama*. Eylül Kitap ve Yayınevi, Ankara.
17. Toros, F.Z., (2001). *Elit Sporcuların Güdüsel Yönelimleri: Voleybolcular Üzerine Bir Araştırma*, Mersin Üniversitesi, Sağlık Bilimleri Enstitüsü, Beden Eğitimi ve Spor Anabilim dalı, Yüksek Lisans Tezi, Mersin.

18. Willis, J. D. and Campbell, L. F. (1992). Exercise psychology. Champaign, IL: Human Kinetics.
19. Wilson, P. M, Rodgers, W.M, Hall, C.R. and Gammage, K.L. (2003). Do autonomous exercise regulations underpin different types of exercise imagery? *Journal of Applied Sport Psychology*, 15.

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